

Development and analysis of initial material of winter spelt wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L. ssp. *spelta*) for productivity breeding

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In the studies of 2019–2024, the productivity indicators of the starting material of winter spelt wheat, created by hybridization with soft winter wheat at Uman National University (Right-Bank Forest-Steppe of Ukraine), were analyzed. In the process of research, spelt wheat samples were identified that can be used in practical selection as donors of genes for certain traits, in particular, high yield (5.25–5.82 t ha⁻¹); semi-dwarfism and low-stemming in breeding for plant height reduction (samples 1786, 1817, 1559, 1674 and 1755; improved grain threshing (91%) and optimal spike structure (samples 95, 155, 1725); high grain protein content (23.8–28.7%), gluten (49.1–57.2%), alveograph indicator (340–425 alveograph units), grain hardness (60.8–68.2 instrument units) in breeding for grain quality (samples 13, 40 and 128). The correlation between productivity indicators was analyzed and it was found that the greatest influence on spelt yield is the quality of grain threshing ($r = 0.89 \pm 0.00$).

Key words: spelt wheat, plant height, threshing quality, yield, grain quality.